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THE APENNINE SIBYL

A MYSTERY AND A LEGEND

A LEGEND FOR A ROMAN PREFECT: THE LAKES OF
PONTIUS PILATE¹

PART 3

17. A resting place in Vienne, France

There is a remarkable passage which is to be found in Flavius Josephus' *The Jewish War*, written at the end of the first century, only a few decades

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after Pontius Pilate's life and remarkable deeds. This excerpt does not refer to Pilate; nonetheless, it will mark the legendary tale of our Roman prefect for the centuries to come.

In Book II, Chapter VII, the Roman-Jewish historian recounts the story of Herod Archelaus, the Ethnarch of Judaea from 4 B.C., when Emperor Augustus enthroned him, up to 6 A.D., when the region was finally reduced to a Roman province under the direct rule of a prefect. In his final days, accusations are brought by the Jews before the Emperor, and Archelaus is removed from his post and then exiled:

«Archelaus took possession of his ethnarchy, and used not the Jews only, but the Samaritans also, barbarously. [...] Whereupon they both sent ambassadors against him to Caesar, and in the ninth year of his government he was banished to Vienne, a city of Gaul, and his effects were put into Caesar's treasury».

Fig. 106 - Herod Archelaus banished to Vienne from Flavius Josephus' *The Jewish War*, with the Greek words for 'Vienne' and 'Gauls' enlarged (manuscript Grec 1425, Bibliothèque Nationale de France, folia 61 and 62)

And another passage on the exile of Herod Archelaus appears in Flavius Josephus' *Antiquities of the Jews* (Book XVII, Chapter XV):

«And when he [Herod Archelaus] had arrived in Rome, Caesar, upon hearing what certain accusers of his had to say, and despite his replies, banished him, and appointed Vienne, a city of Gaul, to be the place of his habitation, and took his money away from him».

Fig. 107 - Vienne and Herod Archelaus in an excerpt from Flavius Josephus' *Antiquities of the Jews*, with the Greek words for 'Vienne, a city of Gaul' highlighted (Greek-Latin edition published in Geneva in 1611, pag. 614)

Vienne, France, not be confused with today's Wien (or 'Vindobona' in Latin): set by the river Rhône, the former capital settlement of the Allobroge Gauls, it was a rich and important town of romanised Gaul, a colony established by Julius Caesar with the name 'Colonia Julia Viennensis', mentioned by an imperial address to the Senate rendered by Emperor Claudius, and by Latin poets like Marcus Valerius Martialis, both celebrating the town's wealth and charming appearance. Still today, we can behold the gorgeous Temple of Augustus and Livia, dating to the first century, standing out at the very centre of the modern town, a shadowy remnant of a glorious past.

This was the place to which Herod Archelaus was banished: a Roman colony set in a northern province of the Empire, far enough from Judaea to be considered as a most fit punishment for a former ruler of the Jews. We must also remember that Vienne is just fifteen miles south of Lyon, or ancient 'Lugdunum', where Archelaus' brother, Herod Antipas, ended his life after having been banished there, too, by Emperor Gaius Caligula.

Fig. 108 - A vision of downtown Vienne, France, with the Temple of Augustus and Livia sitting in the middle of the main central square

The episode concerning Herod Antipas is mentioned by Flavius Josephus himself in his *Antiquities of the Jews* (Book XVIII, Chapter IX):

«[Gaius Caligula] sentenced Herod [Antipas] to perpetual banishment in Lyon, a city of Gaul».

But what has all this story about Vienne and Lyon got to do with Pontius Pilate? Apparently nothing, as Archelaus was exiled twenty years before the Roman prefect started his own rule of Judaea; and Antipas, though living in the same years as Pontius Pilate, is not indicated by Flavius Josephus as having been banished to Gaul together with our Roman prefect, for whom no remark on his final destiny is provided by the Roman-Jews historian.

Fig. 109 - Herod Antipas exiled to Lugdunum, modern Lyon, France, as mentioned in a passage from Flavius Josephus' *Antiquities of the Jews* (Greek-Latin edition published in Geneva in 1611, pag. 638)

However, there are some links, and some queer connections between Herod Archelaus, Herod Antipas and Pilate.

Pontius Pilate was a figure who was in close connection to the life and death of Jesus Christ. Instead, Herod Archelaus had nothing to do with Jesus, yet his relatives had a lot: he was son to Herod the Great, well known to Christians for his alleged role in the Massacre of the Innocents, and also brother to Herod Antipas, the ruler of Galilee who played a major role in the Passion. Together with Pilate himself.

Furthermore, just like Pilate some thirty years later, Herod Archelaus had been reported by his subjects to the Emperor in Rome, owing to his ruthless, predatory administration of the territory and people assigned to his rule. And Herod Antipas, too, had been the target of accusations of treason presented before Gaius Caligula by another Herod, Agrippa.

The confusion between the three, Herod Archelaus, Herod Antipas and Pontius Pilate, was ready to unleash its full potential.

Flavius Josephus had never written that Pontius Pilate had been exiled to Gaul, as he had only reported that Pilate was ordered «to go to Rome, to answer before the Emperor to the accusations of the Jews», and that «before he could get to Rome, Tiberius was dead».

Yet, if Herod Archelaus and Herod Antipas had been banished to the region of Lyon and Vienne, a town that ancient Romans had elected as a suitable place of exile, the same destiny was to be assigned to Pilate by later authors.

And Vienne, France, was to become the place where the earthly life of Pontius Pilate would reach its cursed end:

«Archelaus [...] accused by the Jews for his ruthlessness before Augustus, was exiled to the most noble town of Vienne, in the Gauls. [...] Tetrarch Herod [...] came to Rome; but he was accused by Agrippa and lost his Tetrarchy; he was sent into exile at Vienne, the town in Gaul [...]. Pilate, who had sentenced Jesus Christ to death, was exiled forever in Vienne as well; there, he was so overwhelmed by despair out of Gaius Caligula's questioning, that he stabbed himself with his own hand looking for instant death to escape his sufferings».

[In the original Latin text: «Archelaus [...] accusantibus apud Augustum ferocitatem eius iudaeis, in Viennam urbem Galliae nobilissimam relegatur [...] Herodes tetrarcha [...] Romam venit; sed accusatus ab Agrippa, etiam tetrarchia perdidit; relegatusque exilio, apud Viennam Galliarum urbem [...]. Pilatus qui sententiam dapnationis in Christum dixerat, et ipse perpetuo exilio Vienne recluditur; tantisque ibi inrogante Gaio [Caligula] anguoribus coarctatus est, ut sua se tranfverberans manu malorum compendium mortis celeritate quaesierit»].

Fig. 110 - Herod Archelaus, Herod Antipas and Pontius Pilate all gathered in Vienne as exiles, according to Ado of Vienne's *Chronicles of the Six Ages of the World*, in the section dedicated to the 'Sexta Aetas' (from manuscript Royal MS 13 A XXIII, British Library, folium 1v and folia 41r, 42v and 43r)

These words were written in the ninth century by bishop Ado of Vienne in his *Chronicles of the Six Ages of the World*, and we read them from a beautiful twelfth-century manuscript, the Royal MS 13 A XXIII, preserved at the British Library (folia 41r, 42v and 43r). Vienne: the French town set fifteen miles south of Lyon, by the river Rhône. Now accommodating not only for the two unwilling Herods (Archelaus and Antipas), as already reported by first-century writer Flavius Josephus (who placed the latter in nearby Lyon), but also for another illustrious newcomer, who had got there straight from Judaea, as well: Pontius Pilate.

It is the first time in recorded history that Vienne, Herod Archelaus's and Herod Antipa's place of exile in Gaul, is mentioned as a site connected to the death of Pontius Pilate, the fifth prefect of Judaea. As we already saw in a previous article, Vienne will soon become one of the main resting places for the body of Pilate: a tale that will be told, at the beginning of the thirteenth century, by Stephen of Bourbon in his *Tractatus de diversis materiis predicabilibus*.

The references to Vienne as the location where Pontius Pilate's corpse is buried are not over with bishop Ado's excerpt. Further mentions are found in the subsequent centuries, a clear sign that the story was being successful amid men of letters and oral storytellers.

In the *Historia Scholastica* (which we read from a 1483 manuscripted edition), written in the twelfth century by Petrus Comestor, a French historian and theologian, we stumble upon the many notorious misdeeds associated to Pontius Pilate's rule of Judaea, as already indicated in such classical sources as Flavius Josephus and Philo of Alexandria:

«At that moment Pilate was already dead. At the very beginning of his career he was a young man, and prefect of Judaea since the twelfth year of the rule of Tiberius Caesar, Vitellius being in charge for Syria. Many accusations were put forward before Tiberius against him: he was accused by the Jews of the savage killing of many innocent people. Furthermore, he was accused by complaining Jews of having placed the statues of pagan gods in their temple. In addition to that, he was also accused of having stolen money from the temple's treasure to his own utility and to build an aqueduct in his own house».

[In the original Latin text: «Pilatus ergo mortuus iam erat, qui, ut a principio huius historie pretaxatum est, anno xii imperii tiberii cesaris erat procurator iudeae, Vitellio praeside sirie, et accusatus est in multis apud tiberius. Accusatus est a iudeis de violenta innocentum interfectione. Accusatus est etiam, quod iudeis reclamantibus ponebat imagines gentilium in templo. Accusatus est etiam quia pecuniam repositam in corbonam redegerat in usus suos, inde faciens aqueductum in domum suam»].

Fig. 111 - Pontius Pilate exiled to Vienne as reported in Petrus Comestor's *Historia Scholastica* (manuscripted version edited in Strasbourg in 1483, section *In historia Actuum Apostolorum*, Chapter CLVII)

As we had already the chance to see in previous articles, all that is no news at all. However, Petrus Comestor adds a further piece of information, concerning the place of his exile:

«Because of all this he was banished to Lyon, where he was from, and there he died in the contempt of his own kindred».

[In the original Latin text: «Et pro his omnibus deportatus est in exilium Lugduni unde oriundus erat, ut ibi in opprobrium generis sui moreretur»].

A place for exile, a place for death. And this place is, once again, Vienne, not far from Lyon, France, as further detailed by Petrus Comestor:

«[Pilate] who had been sent into exile at Vienne, where he died» (in the original Latin text: «[Pilatus] qui iam deportatus fuerat in esilium Viennam, et ibi mortuus est»).

In Jean de Mailly 's *Abbreviatio in gestis et miraculis sanctorum* (*A shortened compendium of deeds and miracles of saints*), dating to the middle of the thirteenth century, we find a tale concerning the beheading of St. John the Baptist. And, again, as we can read in thirteenth-century manuscript Latin 10843 preserved at the Bibliothèque Nationale de France, we find Pontius Pilate and Lyon:

«But the subsequent year Pontius Pilate was accused by the Jews [...] before Tiberius of violence and nothing less than the killing of innocent people [...] and for all this, as Flavius Josephus reports, he was exiled to Lyon, the place where he was from, and there he died in the scorn of his kindred. Yet elsewhere is written that he was sentenced there to eat no cooked food, which is a detail that is not reported by Josephus. But he grieved so much of his doom that he eventually killed himself».

[In the original Latin text: «Sed sequenti anno Poncius Pilatus accusatus est a Judeis [...] apud Tyberium de violentia, scilicet innocentium interfectione [...] et pro hiis omnibus, ut dicit Josephus, deportatus est Lugdunum in exilium unde oriundus erat ut ibi in opprobrium generis sui moreretur. Alibi vero legitur quod ita ibi dampnatus est ut nichil coctum comederet, quod Josephus quidem non dicit. Sed tamen tam vehementer doluit ut se ipsum occideret»].

Lyon and Vienne, Vienne and Lyon. According to all concordant sources, Pontius Pilate died and was buried in the region of Lyon, with an additional detail: he ended his life in Vienne.

Fig. 112 - Pilate in Lyon, from Jean de Mailly's *Abbreviatio in gestis et miraculis sanctorum* (manuscript Latin 10843, Département des Manuscrits, Bibliothèque Nationale de France, folia 164r - 164v)

Vienne: not a mere folktale of medieval origin, but a true place of banishment, which ancient Romans had selected as a forcible destination for selected high-rank Jews, as attested by Flavius Josephus in the first century, in the ripeness of the Roman Empire.

This tale, now fully involving Pontius Pilate, experienced so great a success that we find it again repeated and expanded in the *Chronica de duabus civitatibus* written by another bishop, Otto of Freising, at the middle of the twelfth-century (we read this passage from folium 42r of manuscript Car. C. 33 (247) preserved at the Zentralbibliothek in Zürich):

«And Pilate was so struck with chastisements by Caesar [Gaius Galigula], that they say he killed himself with his dagger. [...] Some also report that he was exiled to Vienne, the town of Gaul, and subsequently drowned into the river Rhône. From this occurrence the local people say that ships are endangered when passing by that spot».

[In the original Latin text: «Pilatus quoque a Cesare tantis malis atteritur, ut suo se gladio interfecisse dicatur. [...] Sunt etiam nonnulli, qui eum apud Viennam urbem Galliae in exilium trusum ac post in Rhodano mersum dicant. Unde usque hodie naves ibi periclitari ab incolis affirmantur»].

Fig. 113 - Pontius Pilate ends its earthly life in the river Rhône by Vienne (Otto of Freising's *Chronica de duabus civitatibus*, manuscript Car. C. 33 (247), Zentralbibliothek, Zürich, folium 42r)

Vienne, again. With an additional element, a highly remarkable one indeed: the ships cruising the Rhône are «endangered» when they sail by the exact place where the corpse of Pontius Pilate was thrown into the waters.

Why was this amazing remark included?

It is worthy of notice that this sentence seems to have something in common with the description of the burial place of Caiaphas, the priest of the Jews, as depicted in the *Rescriptum Tiberii*: «the ground would not receive him at all, but cast him out».

What is the meaning of all that?

Before we start treading this remarkable clue, we need to complete our journey into Pilate's many burial places.

It will be a matter of life and death. And of golden legends. Let's go and get into the great medieval success of the gloomy legend of Pontius Pilate's death.

18. A mountain and a demonic burial place

«Pilate grew up as a sensible youth, endowed with the twin virtues of body and mind».

[In the original Latin text: «Crevit Pilatus et fit prudens adolescens, corporis et mentis gemina virtute nitescens»].

Fig. 114 - A young Pontius Pilate as staged in the opening section of *De Vita Pilati* (manuscript LIP 51, Leiden University, folium 114v)

This is a passage taken from the opening section of the ancient poem *De Vita Pilati* (*The Life of Pilate*), a work dating back, according to scholars, to the twelfth century, but most certainly originating from earlier oral storytelling.

This anonymous work, designed for public readings to be held before delighted audiences, was a most successful piece of literary narration across the Middle Ages, with many manuscripted copies scattered and subsequently retrieved across Europe. *De Vita Pilati* stages one of the most intriguing and riveting characters which are portrayed in the Gospels: Pontius Pilate, a popular figure who used to cast his peculiar fascination on people belonging to all social classes; the man who had ventured himself as far as to deliver Jesus Christ, the Son of God, to a harrowing death.

In the nearly four hundred Latin verses of *De Vita Pilati*, the wicked traits of the prefect of Judaea are greatly emphasized: a representation typical of Middle Ages, according to the antique tradition, mainly operating in the

western territories of Europe, which was specifically promoted by Pope St. Gregory the Great with his description of Pontius Pilate as a blood-curdling «limb of the Fiend».

Let's read *De Vita Pilati* from manuscript LIP 51, preserved at the Leiden University, The Netherlands (folia 114r - 118v), with the aid of a transcript provided by the French scholar Edélestand du Méril in his *Poésies populaires latines du Moyen Age* (1847, pag. 343 - 357).

Fig. 115 - The first folium of *De Vita Pilati* (manuscript LIP 51, Leiden University, folium 114r)

Born in the German province's town of Mainz («Moguntia»), the «sensible youth», the son of a king, soon becomes a nasty playmate to his young companions, until «a child is ruthlessly murdered by another child» (in the original Latin text: «puer a puero crudeli morte necatur»). The atrocious crime perpetrated by the young Pilate is soon discovered, and would certainly deserve a death sentence; yet his life is spared and he is sent to Rome as a hostage, never to be set free («Romam transmissus obses, numquam redimatur»).

According to *De Vita Pilati*, when in Rome his evil temper manifested itself once again: he becomes a friend to the son of a king of Britain, a hostage himself; but, as if it had turned into a sort of cruel habit for him, he cuts the throat of his new acquaintance («puerum, sicut fratrem proprium, jugulavit»). Again, he is not put to death owing to his birth and status: he is rather exiled to the island of Pontus, inhabited by barbaric people. There, he rules the island and its unmanageable dwellers, gaining for himself the additional epithet of «Pontius» (in the original Latin text: «Auxit ei nomen locus hic, est namque vocatus - Pontius a Ponto, sublimi sede locatus»).

Fig. 116 - Pilate named after the island of Pontus («auxit ei nomen locus hic, est namque vocatus - Pontius a Ponto, sublimi sede locatus», *De Vita Pilati*, manuscript LIP 51, Leiden University, folium 115r)

The story runs fast towards its ghastly end. Pilate moves to Judaea. The Passion takes place. After Jesus' crucifixion, Emperor Titus is portrayed as being afflicted with leprosy. He is informed of the miracles carried out by Jesus in Judaea, and issues an order to find him and bring him to Rome to cure his disease. But a woman (not named, but the figure is that of Saint Veronica) informs the Emperor that Jesus was killed by Pilate and then rose again and ascended to heaven. In the final verses, Pilate is summoned to Rome before the court of Titus, who is determined to punish him for his role in the crucifixion of Jesus. And, in the capital city of the Roman Empire, the Emperor's rage unleashes unrestrained: it is commanded that he shall «die of an extraordinarily ghastly death, dismembered by wild beasts» (in the original Latin text: «necandus turpi morte nimis feris lacerandus»).

These are the final hours in the life of Pontius Pilate. Overwhelmed by fear and despair, he cuts his throat with a knife, dying in his own dripping blood, thus concluding his life with an unholy gesture, in this way anticipating the punishment that was about to fall on him (in the original Latin text: «tactusque dolore, cultello fodit jugulum, manante cruore occidit infelix, et poenas anticipando perfidiae summam concludit fine nefando»).

Fig. 117 - Pilate, sentenced to a harrowing death, escapes his punishment by killing himself (*De Vita Pilati*, manuscript LIP 51, Leiden University, folia 117r and 117v)

Is Pontius Pilate's earthly journey over? Not in the least.

Because at this point of the narrative, the body of Pilate begins its own, doomed journey. The cursed journey of a corpse which is part of the body of Satan:

«It was devised that his corpse was not to be buried - it was to be brought far away and cast - into the Rhône, concealed beneath the swirling eddies of the river - But in that place frenzied commotions began to occur - so that any ship that travelled by that spot - immediately vanished into the whirlpool and sank to the abyss».

[In the original Latin text: «Hunc extinctum non miserunt tumulari - sed procul a patria jusserunt praecipitari - in Rhodanum, latuitque diu sub fluminis unda - Sed huic mansit rabies quaedam furibunda - nam naves quaecunque locum transire volebant - gurgitis extemplo pereuntes ima petebant»].

Fig. 118 - Pilate's body is cast into the river Rhône (*De Vita Pilati*, LIP 51, Leiden University, folium 117v)

Again, the river Rhône. Again, the endangered ships, like in Otto of Freising's *Chronica de duabus civitatibus*.

Is this place by the Rhône the city of Vienne again? Yes, as the unknown author of *De Vita Pilati* adds in subsequent lines:

«Beholding that, the inhabitants of Vienne, amazed by this new evil - went to Lyon determined to find the reason for all that» [in the original Latin text: «Unde Viennenses, novitate mali stupefacti - Lugdunum veniunt causam perquirere facti»].

Fig. 119 - The inhabitants of Vienne goes to Lyon, with the Latin words for the two towns highlighted (*De Vita Pilati*, manuscript LIP 51, Leiden University, folium 117v)

Why did the citizens of Vienne directed themselves to the main town in the region? Because there they would address the high priests («pontifices coeunt») and, at the presence of all the people, they would raise a plea to

God («auxiliumque Dei communi voce precantur») that this awesome curse might cease («pestis miseranda quiescat»).

The burial place of Pontius Pilate is not a resting place. Something happens at the very spot where he had been thrown into the waters of the river Rhône.

Something evil. Something dreadful. Something abominable.

And “De Vita Pilati” continues with its horrific tale. The whole community sets up a trial ship, hallowed by the presence of holy relics, and, with no crew on board, lets it slide on the river until the boat gets to the very spot where that loathsome corpse had been submerged («inque locum veniens, quo perditus ille jacebat»). All the people follow, praying God and praising Him with sacred songs. And Pilate remains quiet in a ghastly silence:

«All was still, and nothing stirred from the deep» [in the original Latin text: «constitit et nulla penitus se parte movebat»].

Now people know that the power of God is stronger than the iniquity of the Evil. With the help of a dredging barge they sieve the muds at the bottom of the river («amnis machinis lustrare profundum») until, their action blessed by the Heaven, they find the abominable body («et nutu Domini mox invenere malignum»).

What happens next? Where is this hateful body to be buried now?

Something is going to happen that will originate unexpected, far-reaching effects on a small lake placed in the middle of Italy, on the Sibillini Mountain Range.

Because the fiendish corpse of Pontius Pilate, a portion of the body of Satan, an execrable limb of the Fiend, is transferred to a new burial site.

And this time it is set within the most elevated mountains:

«A place is amid the Alps, as is recorded from which direful flames visibly erupt. They dragged Pilate and cast him into it

to be consumed by the fire of Hell, as he deserved.
Often the voices of demons can be heard there,
fiends who rejoice of the death and punishments of the damned [...] and so the antique curse of the troubled waters ended at last».

[In the original Latin text:
«Alpibus in mediis locus est, sicut memoratur
horripifer et flammis a se proferre probatur
In quem Pilatum traxerunt praecipitandum
atque gehennali, sicut decet, igne cremandum.
Vox ibi multotiens auditur daemoniorum
gaudia sunt quorum mors et poenae miserorum [...] cessavitque vetus submersio pestis iniquae»].

Fig. 120 - A burial place in the Alps erupting hellish flames (*De Vita Pilati*, manuscript LIP 51, Leiden University, folium 117v)

We started from Vienne, France. We began with a river, the Rhône. However, the corpse of Pontius Pilate, cursed by God himself and celebrated by the demons as a member of their own fiendish essence, is soon transferred to a most suitable place.

A place that might hold him as far away as possible from the human race. A place in which his wicked body might be disposed of in the most suitable way. A place of flames. A place of doom. A place of Hell.

Fig. 121 - The Latin words for 'Alps', 'flames', 'hellish' and 'demons' highlighted (*De Vita Pilati*, manuscript LIP 51, Leiden University, folium 117v)

In this legendary tale, certainly arising from a number of oral variations, Pilate's body is sent into a burning pit set in the Alps, the highest, most inaccessible mountains in Europe.

Fig. 122 - A vision of the Alps in the region of Lausanne, which is one of Pontius Pilate's subsequent resting places according to the medieval tradition

Has it anything to do with the Sibillini Mountain Range? Not yet. However, we are getting closer and closer to the precipitous peaks which raise in central Italy. And to the lakes sitting within their blood-curdling glacial cirque.

But the journey of Pilate's corpse is not over yet. We still have to follow its winding route across Europe. So let's take this ride, because our journey is not yet over.

19. Rivers, pits and mountains (but none in Italy)

Pontius Pilate, a cursed corpse. Since the early-Christian age a tradition, mainly propagating itself in the western territories of Europe, had identified the fifth prefect of Judaea as a «diaboli membrum», a limb of the body of the Fiend, according to the horrific words pronounced by Pope St. Gregory the Great in his homilies.

So, the circumstances of his death and the fate of his dead body began to be the subject of a number of oral tales, which here and then consolidated into written passages, remarks and full pieces of narratives, each one adding, one way or the other, to the fantastic picture of a doomed Pilate, deprived of any rest even though he had already passed away, as a result of a suicidal act or a harrowing death inflicted by the Emperor of Rome as a punishment for the prefect's role in the crucifixion of Jesus Christ.

Fig. 123 - Pontius Pilate and the Passion of Jesus Christ

In the early Middle Ages, the tales began to point to a specific burial place for Pilate: the river Rhône, by the town of Vienne, France, a settlement already openly mentioned by ancient author Flavius Josephus as a banishment place for Herod Archelaus, while his brother Herod Antipas was portrayed as having been exiled to nearby Lyon.

At that very point in the river, the waters were shaken by demonic turmoils, which put all sailing ships at risk. In addition to that, twelfth-century *De Vita Pilati* added a further piece of information: the cursed body was recovered from the eddying waters and brought to a specific location set amid the Alps, the most elevated mountains in Europe; there, he was cast into a hellish pits, where flames and demons welcomed it.

Where was this burning pit situated, amid the Alps? Do we have any medieval account which tells us the location of the ultimate resting place of Pontius Pilate?

As we already mentioned at the beginning of this series of articles, in the first half of the thirteenth century a Dominican preacher, Stephen of Bourbon, wrote in his *Tractatus de diversis materiis predicabilibus* the following information on Pontius Pilate, Vienne, and some mountain lying nearby, partly drawing his words from Jean de Mailly's *Abbreviatio in gestis et miraculis sanctorum*:

«Others say that in Lyon he [Pontius Pilate] was condemned to be hanged, and he was actually hanged at Vienne [...] And not far from that same place, on a mount near St. Chamon, he [Pilate] was hurled into a pit; from this pit, when a stone was thrown in it, they say vapours are issued, and storms arouse».

[In the original Latin text: «Alii dicunt quod Lugduni suspendio adjudicatus et apud Viennam est suspensus [...] et ibi prope in monte supra Saint Chamon in puteo projectus; ubi, quando lapis proicitur, fumus inde egredi dicitur, de quo tempestas concitatur»].

Stephen of Bourbon was born in the French town of Belleville, by the river Rhône, and only a few miles from Lyon. According to his writing, the mysterious mountain with the hellish pit which would contain the body of Pilate is located near Saint-Chamond, again in the territory of Lyon. And

there, the adjacent relief, still today, is called the 'Massif de Pilat', the mountain range of Pilate, whose main peak is the 'Mont de Pilat'.

Thus, the demonic burial place of the prefect of Judaea seems to wander around Lyon, first in the Rhône, and then on a nearby mountain, in a pit which emits smoke and arouses storms. On the other hand, *De Vita Pilati* indicates the Alps as Pilate's resting place, with ancillary flames and demons included.

Fig. 124 - The early mentions of burial places for Pontius Pilate are linked to the region of Lyon and the Alps, with no reference to Italy

One major piece of information must be noted: no medieval account on Pontius Pilate points, in any way, to the area of the Sibillini Mountain Range, in Italy.

So what's next? Have we finished with Pilate's roaming across the rivers and mountains of Europe? Not in the least. Because the next step will bring our search into another medieval text, a best seller of its age: the *Legenda Aurea*.

And we will stumble upon further astounding findings.

20. The *Legenda Aurea* and an ultimate resting place

More than one thousand ancient manuscripts surviving from the Middle Ages. An impressive diffusion across all European countries and regions. A popular work, used by preachers to develop their sermons, read in churches and known by people belonging to all social classes. An encyclopedic accumulation of fascinating stories, which were intended for the moral and spiritual edification of the devotees, but also capable of entertain and amaze with the wondrous character of the tales included in this pious collection.

Fig. 125 - The opening of the *Legenda Aurea* from fourteenth-century manuscript Latin 9730, preserved at the Bibliothèque Nationale de France, Département des Manuscrits (folium 1r)

We are referring to the *Legenda Aurea*, the *Golden Legend*, or, with a more accurate translation, *Golden stories that must be read*, a masterpiece of medieval culture written by Jacobus de Varagine, a Dominican friar and bishop from the Italian town of Genoa, who lived between 1228 and 1298.

His collection of tales about the life and death of more than a hundred fifty saints, also including a number of chapters dedicated to all principal Christian festivities, soon became a landmark for the preaching activities of his own Dominicans, whose exact name was 'Order of the Preachers', out of the fluent, simple Latin used by Jacobus and the extraordinary effort to rework different hagiographic traditions, with a final, fully consistent merging which resulted into a highly readable, if not enjoyable, text full of tales concerning the most renowned saints, their miraculous deeds and their heroic martyrdoms as witnesses to the true faith.

The narrative set down by Jacobus was intended to convey a vision of martyred saints as hallowed men and women who establish a triumphant link between the living men and the Divine, through the sacrifice of their own lives for the glorification of God. And, with this aim in mind, he did not forget to include legendary passages taken from apocryphal material: excerpts which are full of a sense of wonder that well suits the character of the whole work, open to larger audiences and dedicated to multiple sorts of readers.

Fig. 126 - Another fine instance of the *Legenda Aurea*, with the chapter on St. John the Baptist as it appears in late-fifteenth-century illuminated manuscript Rps BOZ 11, preserved at the Biblioteka Narodowa (National Library of Poland), at page 93

From now on, everybody would know the story of Pontius Pilate and his troubled, demonic resting place.

And which fiendish resting place will the *Legenda Aurea* choose to mention? Will Jacobus de Varagine report the old, illustrious tale of Vienne and the river Rhône? Will the *Legenda* name any mountains in the Alps, following a more recent tradition we already saw in previous articles? Or, maybe, will it provide a first, never-heard-before reference to the Lakes of Pilatus, in the Sibillini Mountain Range?

Let's open the vellum pages of manuscript NAL 1747 preserved at the Département des Manuscrits of the Bibliothèque Nationale de France. Dating back to the thirteenth century, it is one of the most ancient manuscripts bearing the text of the *Legenda Aurea*.

And there, at Folium 92r, after a long introductory sermon on the Passion, Jacobus de Varagine enumerates the names of those who delivered Jesus Christ to a harrowing death: Judas, the Jews, and, of course, Pilate. Then Jacobus writes the following words:

Fig. 128 - The excerpt on Judas, the Jews and Pilate in the *Legenda Aurea* from manuscript NAL 1747, preserved at the Bibliothèque Nationale de France (folium 92r)

«About the punishment and origin of Judas, the narrative can be retrieved in the tale of St. Matthew; about the punishment and slaughter of the Jews you can read in the tale of St. James the Less; furthermore, about the punishment and origin of Pilate it is possible to read the account in some apocryphal narrative».

[In the original Latin text: «De poena et origine Judae invenies in legenda sancti Matthiae, de poena et excidio Judaeorum in legenda sancti Jacobi minoris, de poena autem et origine Pilati in quadam historia licet apocrypha legitur»].

The apocryphal narrative referred to by the *Legenda Aurea* is *De Vita Pilati*, the ancient poem dating to more than a century earlier, which we illustrated in a previous article. Jacobus de Varagine draws a large quantity of material from that apocryphal tale, starting his account from the birth of Pilate (with some changes with respect to *De Vita Pilati*) and then continuing with the early murder perpetrated by the young prefect-to-be against his half-brother, both being the sons of a same king in this version of the story. Exactly like in *De Vita Pilati*, Pilate is exiled to Rome as a hostage, and there he proceeds to kill the son of a king of the Franks, a hostage like himself. Again, he is sent to the uncivilized island of Pontus as a punishment, where he subjugates the local population and gains for himself the epithet of Pontius.

Up to now, this is precisely the same account already told by *De Vita Pilati*. And the *Legenda Aurea* runs on the very same track, with Pontius Pilate now called to Judaea by Herod, they being initially friends and then competitors for the power in the region. When Jesus is crucified, Pilate begins to fear that his own deeds would be considered as an «offense to Tiberius Caesar, as he had sentenced innocent blood to death» (in the original Latin text: «[...] offensam Tyberii Caesarii eo quod condemnasset sanguinem innocentem»).

Again, like in *De Vita Pilati* (but there the Emperor was Titus), Tiberius is afflicted by a serious illness («morbo gravi teneretur»). The news of the miracles carried out by Jesus Christ arrive in the capital city of the Empire, and Tiberius commands to have that amazing Jew brought to Rome, in the hope of a cure for his disease. When in Jerusalem, his delegate is informed by a woman, St. Veronica (she is openly named in the *Legenda Aurea*), that

Jesus was condemned and crucified by order of Pontius Pilate himself. So Pilate is taken and brought to Rome, where he is forced to face the Emperor's rage, though abated by a miraculous soothing effect created on Tiberius by Jesus' tunic, which Pilate had brought with him from Jerusalem and was wearing before the Emperor (another legendary tale integrated by Jacobus in his own account).

Yet the above wondrous event will not save Pilate's life, and Tiberius will pronounce fatal words against him:

«Thus a sentence was issued upon Pilate, that he shall die of a ghastly death».

[In the original Latin text: «Data est igitur in Pilatum sententia, ut morte turpissima damnaretur»].

However, as depicted in *De Vita Pilati*, the former prefect of Judaea anticipates his own death sentence: «hearing of his doom, he killed himself with his own knife, ending up his life by this sort of death» (in the original Latin text: «audiens hoc Pylatus cultello proprio se necavit et tali morte vitam finivit»).

Fig. 129 - Pontius Pilate sentenced to death and committing suicide in the *Legenda Aurea* from manuscript NAL 1747, preserved at the Bibliothèque Nationale de France (folium 93v)

And now, a most astounding section of the tale begins.

Because Jacobus de Varagine, as in his own habit, contrives a brilliant merger of the many legendary traditions concerning the corpse of Pontius

Pilate and his successive resting places. And, in this multifaceted form, he will consign that gloomy myth to history.

First, we find something unexpected. Owing to the fact that Pilate's suicide occurs in Rome, his body too finds its initial burial site into a most renowned river which flows through the city, the Tiber:

«After having tied his dead body to a heavy weight, it was thrown into the river Tiber».

[In the original Latin text: «Moli igitur ingenti alligatur et in Tyberim flumen immergitur»].

Yet that corpse was too unholy to simply rest in peace; and the result was no different from what earlier legends used to tell about the blood-curdling turmoils that affected the Rhône:

«But abominable, fiendish demons, rejoicing of that fiendish, abominable corpse, began to stir amazing waves, carrying it off now in the water and now in the air, and aroused lightnings, storms, thunders and hail up in the air so appallingly, that everybody was seized by a ghastly dread».

Fig. 130 - Pilate thrown into the Tiber (the word is highlighted) with the resulting turmoil in the *Legenda Aurea* from manuscript NAL 1747, preserved at the Bibliothèque Nationale de France (folium 93v)

[In the original Latin text: «Spiritus vero maligni et sordidi corpori maligno et sordido congaudentes et nunc in aquis nunc in aere rapientes mirabiles inundationes in aquis movebant et fulgura, tempestates, tonitrua et grandines in aere terribiliter generabant, ita ut cuncti timore horribili tenerentur»].

This horrifying description of the interaction between the corpse of Pilate, a limb of the Fiend in St. Gregory's writings, and the waters inhabited by demonic shadows is a vision that will mark the legendary tale of the Roman prefect for the centuries to come.

However, Jacobus' tale is not over. This is only the first step of a ghastly journey of that corpse. A second step follows at once, and this is a step we already know well:

«Owing to these events, the Romans drew him out from the river Tiber and, as an outrage, fetched the corpse to Vienne and cast it into the Rhône. In fact 'Vienne' was intended as a sort of 'Gehenna', a place of damnation; or, better, 'Bienne' was the name given to the town because it had been built in two years».

Fig. 131 - Pilate transferred to Vienne and the river Rhône (the words are highlighted) in the *Legenda Aurea* from manuscript NAL 1747, preserved at the Bibliothèque Nationale de France (folium 93v)

[In the original Latin text: «Quapropter Romani eum a Tyberis fluvio extrahentes derisionis causa ipsum Viennam deportaverunt et Rhodano fluvio immerserunt. Vienna enim dicitur quasi via Gehennae, quia erat tunc

locus maledictionis, vel potius dicitur Bienna eo quod, ut dicitur, biennio sit constructa»].

The body of Pontius Pilate has now reached Vienne, France, which had been its legendary burial place since the ninth century, when bishop Ado of Vienne, in his *Chronicles of the Six Ages of the World*, had indicated that town as the deportation site of Herod and Pilate, both exiled from Galilee and Judaea to the Roman province of Gaul. Vienne: the town that, since the first century, was indicated by Flavius Josephus as the exile place of Herod Archelaus. And Jacobus de Varagine sticks to this ancient tradition, even though he indulges in presenting his reader with a couple of surmises on the role of Vienne in this tale, without succeeding in being plausible and persuading.

At any rate, the *Legenda Aurea* has more to say on it. As we already know, Pilate is not a quiet figure even when dead:

«But the evil spirits did not desert this place, just like it had occurred in Rome: they acted the same way, so the people there, unable to bear such a haunting plague of demons, removed that curse far from themselves and consigned it to a burial place in the territory of the town of Lausanne».

[In the original Latin text: «Sed ibi nequam spiritus effluunt, ibidem eadem operantes, homines ergo illi tantam infestationem daemonum non ferentes vas illud maledictionis a se removerunt et illud sepeliendum Lausanae civitatis territorio commiserunt»].

Fig. 132 - Pilate is transferred from the river Rhône to Lausanne (the word is highlighted) in the *Legenda Aurea* from manuscript NAL 1747, preserved at the Bibliothèque Nationale de France (folium 93v)

Here we are: we have just got to the Alps, the mountains that were first indicated as Pilate's burial place in *De Vita Pilati*. And we finally arrived in Switzerland, by Lausanne, the town which was also mentioned in a thirteenth-century anonymous commentary to the *Speculum regum*, written a century earlier by Godfrey of Viterbo, as we already illustrated at the very beginning of our long travel into this legendary tale.

Have we finished? Not in the least.

Let's continue our read from the *Legenda Aurea*'s chapter on the Passion, because a fourth and final resting place is about to appear:

«However those who were overwhelmed by that same plague as described before, resolved to remove it from themselves, so they hurled the body into a certain pit set amid the mountains, from which people say that deceptive illusions created by the demons are visible in their agitation still today».

[In the original Latin text: «Qui cum nimis praefatis infestationibus gravarentur, ipsam a se removerunt et in quodam puteo montibus circumsepto immerserunt, ubi adhuc relatione quorundam quaedam dyabolicae machinationes ebullire videntur»].

Fig. 133 - Pilate is finally thrown into an abyss amid the mountains (the words 'pit' and 'montibus' are highlighted) in the “Legenda Aurea” from manuscript NAL 1747, preserved at the Bibliothèque Nationale de France (folium 93v)

At last, we have concluded our ghastly journey together with Pontius Pilate's cursed corpse: we started from the Tiber in Rome; then we moved to the Rhône, France; subsequently we landed near Lausanne, Switzerland; and we ended our travel into a pit hidden amid the Swiss Alps. That is, the

same place we also found in *De Vita Pilati* (a «place amid the Alps» which used to erupt «direful flames», full of rejoicing demons) and in the commentary to the *Speculum regum* (from which «storms and hail and lightnings and thunders» raised).

«This account», concludes Jacobus de Varagine in his *Legenda Aurea*, «can be read in the said apocryphal history» («Hucusque in praedicta historia apocrypha leguntur»).

And this is the account that the *Legenda Aurea* will spread across Europe from the thirteenth century onwards. Audiences of all kinds, from devotees in churches to aristocrats in their castles, will be reading those words, dreaming of the horrifying doom that Pontius Pilates, once a Roman prefect, experienced after his own death.

Here we arrived. But is there any space, in this story, for the Sibillini Mountain Range and its Lakes of Pilatus?

No. There is no space. They are never mentioned. Rome is in there, and Vienne, and Lausanne, and also Lucerne. But the Sibillini Mountain Range are never present.

In all the ancient sources we perused, up to the *Legenda Aurea*, there is not the slightest trace of this portion of the Apennines, set in the middle of Italy.

So where do we go from here?

Let's proceed into the next chapter, and we will try to find a direction.

21. Why is the Sibillini Mountain Range missing?

Our amazing journey into the legendary tale of the myth concerning Pontius Pilate and his death is almost reaching its conclusion. And now it is time to go back to our initial questions.

We know that in central Italy rises the Sibillini Mountain Range, a portion of the Apennines. We know that within that massive ridge stands Mount Vettore, a giant, arched mountain which dominates the region with its precipitous cliffs. We know that this titanic mountain contains a special, sinister place, a colossal glacial cirque, enshrouded in a silence of death. There, two small lakes filled with icy waters, known as the Lakes of Pilate, reflect the sky above.

Fig. 134 - The Lakes of Pilate in the Sibillini Mountain Range, Italy

Antoine de la Sale, in his *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl*, reports that this is the burial place of Pontius Pilate, the fifth prefect of Roman-occupied Judaea. The site is attended by necromancer who perform their ghastly arts. When this occurs, violent storms are stirred and the region gets ruined.

Are the lakes which are set in the middle of the Sibillini Mountain Range in Italy listed in Pilate's legendary tale as burial place for the Roman governor?

The answer is no.

Throughout the centuries, in the previous chapters we had the chance to clearly perceive the mythical route treaded by the dead, cursed body of Pilate in search of an impossible rest. And the Sibillini Mountain Range never pops up.

Let's summarize here the many findings we stumbled upon during our search.

Fig. 135 - The Lake of Pilate as portrayed in Antoine de la Sale's *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* (manuscript no. 0653 (0924), Bibliothèque du Château (Musée Condé), Chantilly, France, folium 1r)

From the Tiber to the Rhône. From Rome to Vienne. And then from Vienne to Lausanne. From two different rivers to a demonic pit in the Alps. This was the ghastly destiny of the cursed body of a dead man: a corpse who had belonged to a prefect of Judaea, who had lived in the time when Jesus Christ was nailed to a Cross for the salvation of the whole mankind.

This loathsome corpse has made a long journey through the centuries: the corpse of Pontius Pilate, the man who had sentenced the Son of God to death: despised by ancient writers like Flavius Josephus and Philo of Alexandria; depicted in the Gospels as an irresolute ruler; considered as a sort of prospect Christian by Quintus Septimius Florens Tertullianus; portrayed in the act of writing amazed reports about Jesus to his Emperor in Rome by Eusebius of Caesarea and Paulus Orosius; acquitted of all charges by Origen of Alexandria, Augustine of Hippo and subsequently Erasmus of Rotterdam, who rather preferred to condemn the Jews, Pontius Pilate's shadowy figure has been portrayed in turn as an intense witness to the Resurrection and a nasty slave to the Fiend.

In the apocryphal literature, such as the *Letter to Emperor Claudius*, the *Gesta Pilati*, contained in the *Gospel of Nicodemus*, the *Anaphora Pilati*, the *Paradosis Pilati* and the *Letter to Tiberius* he manifestly provides an astonished testimony to the divine nature of Jesus Christ, and he is eventually enlisted within the ranks of the saints in the Ethiopian Orthodox Church: Pontius Pilate, a holy man.

On the other hand, a very different portrait of the Roman prefect has been handed down to us by the Western tradition. It was Celsus who first compared Pilate to Pentheus, the ancient king who put divine Dionysus in chains, and was horribly punished for that. Then Emperor Maximinus II had commissioned forged reports, to be ascribed to Pilate, with a view to discrediting Christians. Subsequently, Aurelius Ambrosius declared that the prefect was a malevolent judge subject to the power of darkness, and St. Gregory I the Great stated that he was a limb of the Devil's body. All this gave rise to the tradition, contained in apocryphal texts such as the *Vindicta Salvatoris*, on his being recalled to Rome, summoned by Tiberius or even Vespasian, to meet the Emperor's rage. Punishments begin to follow, with Pilate being bricked up in a cave (*Epistola Tiberii ad Pilatum*) and his fellow-culprit Caiaphas being rejected by the earth as his body is buried beneath the ground.

In the early Middle Ages, the gloominess of the legend deepens further: John of Antioch, the Byzantine *Suda*, George Kedrenos describe the death sentence pronounced on Pilate by the Emperor of Rome, with the punishment ranging from sheer beheading to the antique «*poena cullei*», especially designed for parricides.

Then, on this legendary stage a town appears, and it is Vienne, in France, with its nearby river, the Rhône. The first to mention it in connection to Pontius Pilate is Ado of Vienne in the ninth century. But Vienne was already well known to all men of letters as the town in ancient Gaul to which the Emperor of Rome had banished Herod Archelaus, according to Flavius Josephus. Pilate and Archelaus had both ruled ancient Judaea, with a thirty-year interval between the two, so confusion sprang up, also in consideration of the major roles played by both Pilate and Herod Antipas, Archelaus' brother, in the Passion of Jesus Christ.

Vienne, France: a territory which is subsequently quoted by Otto of Freising and Petrus Comestor as well, with the addition of a plunge of the body into the Rhône and some weird commotion of the waters at the very spot where the burial occurred. Then we get to *De Vita Pilati*, with its comprehensive tale concerning Pilate's early life and a detailed account of his prosecution, death by suicide and burial into the Rhône, followed by an eerie commotion in the waters, the recovery of the corpse, and its removal to a hellish pit set amid the Alps.

Stephen of Bourbon, too, mentioned a demonic pit, this time set not too far from Vienne. But, then, it will be Jacobus de Varagine, with its *Legenda Aurea*, who will consecrate the ultimate version of the tale about the final doom of Pontius Pilate's body: the Tiber, then the Rhône, and then some burial ground in Lausanne, and finally a pit in the Alps, and in all the listed places demons would grimly rejoice during their ghastly encounter with the cursed corpse.

Across this intricate, bimillennial tradition, can we retrieve any mention of the Sibillini Mountain Range?

The answer is, again, no.

Fig. 136 - The sinister landscape within the glacial cirque of Mount Vettore, in which the Lakes of Pilate are nested

They are never mentioned. Nobody ever says that the body of Pontius Pilate has found his burial place in a certain lake nested within that mountainous massif in Italy.

The Sibillini Mountain Range is not listed. The Italian peaks, magically named after a Sibyl, are totally missing.

So what do they have to do with the legend of Pilate? Why did Antoine de la Sale include them in this gloomy, peculiar lore? Was the French gentleman wrong when he reported the tale of the lakes as connected to the myth of the Roman prefect? And who was the first to mention them as part of this ancient tradition?

Fig. 137 - Another view of the Lake of Pilate as depicted in Antoine de la Sale's *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* (manuscript no. 0653 (0924), Bibliothèque du Château (Musée Condé), Chantilly, France, folium 5v)

Let's turn to the next chapter and try to find the answers to all the above questions.

22. The Apennine variant of an ancient lore

In the previous chapters, we saw that no medieval reference exists that may establish a link between the legend of Pontius Pilate and the Sibillini Mountain Range in Italy.

As an actual fact, according to the known sources of the legend, Pilate was buried in many different places, but no one of them is situated in the mountainous chain which is part of the Italian Apennines.

However, in the year 1420 Antoine de la Sale, in his *Paradise of Queen Sibyl*, provides a testimony to the fact that the gloomy legend of Pontius Pilate had reached the Sibillini Mountain Range, and had unmistakably established there.

Fig. 138 - A magnified view of the words «Lake of Pilate» drawn on a miniature contained in Antoine de la Sale's *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* (manuscript no. 0653 (0924), Bibliothèque du Château (Musée Condé), Chantilly, France, folium 5v)

«Tales are told», writes Antoine de la Sale, «that when Titus son of Vespasian, the Emperor of Rome, had crushed down the town of Jerusalem, which some say that it was made to avenge the death of Our Lord Jesus Christ [...] when he came back to Rome he brought with him Pilate who at that time was an officier at the said town of Jerusalem». To our experienced ears, the above sentences sound as something we have already heard of: it is the tale we read in the *Legenda Aurea* and *De Vita Pilati* and the *Paradosis Pilati* and the *Vindicta Salvatoris*, and other apocryphal texts.

And it is not by a casual chance that the French author echoes the name of that same Vespasian who is also mentioned in the *Vindicta*, even though this Emperor was not a contemporary of the Roman prefect: same sources, same historical mistakes.

It is clear that when Antoine de la Sale reported the tales told to him by the local people of the Sibillini Mountain Range, he was listening to one of the many variants of the mythical tale concerning Pontius Pilate and his execrable body, a limb of the Fiend as first expressed by Pope Gregory I at the end of the sixth century. The tale was the same, but the place - the Sibillini Mountain Range - was not one of the canonical burial sites listed in well-known sources such as the *Legenda Aurea*.

Unequivocally enough, in a significant passage of the *Paradise of Queen Sibyl*, Antoine de la Sale mentions the very rationale of the whole mythical tale which narrates of Pontius Pilate as we know it from the most ancient sources, dating back to the earliest centuries of Christianity:

«He [the Emperor] decided to put him to death on the ground that Pilate had not intended to sentence our true saviour Jesus Christ, yet he had failed in his duty to preserve him from death».

[In the original French text: «Il [l'empereur] le fist mourir suppose que pillate ne voullist oncques condampner nostredit vray sauveur Jhesuscrist mais pour ce quil ne fist son devoir a le garantir de mort»].

This is the very core of the mythical guilt of Pontius Pilate, as we read in the *Paradosis Pilati* («you should have guarded him [Jesus] from the Jews»), in the *Rescriptum Tiberii* («just as you condemned this one unjustly and delivered him to death»), in the words written by Eusebius of Caesarea («Pilate himself, who was an unjust judge to the Saviour») and Aurelius Ambrosius («a judge must never give in to malevolence or fear, lest he barter innocent blood [...] He did not restrain from uttering an unholy sentence»): the Roman governor chose not to preserve the life of Jesus Christ and, out of fear and cowardice, showed Him the way to the Cross.

Again, the tale we find amid the Sibillini Mountain Range, in Italy, at the beginning of the fifteenth century, belongs to the very same corpus of

legendary traditions which make up the ancient lore about Pontius Pilate, his guilt, his death, his burial places.

And the account retrieved by Antoine de la Sale in this remote corner of Italy in the year 1420 contains another fundamental element which is a characteristic mark of the whole legend about the Roman prefect.

The lake, continues de la Sale, «is strictly guarded [...] on the ground that when anybody comes to it covertly and performs the art of the Fiend, after the operation is made a storm so violent raises in the region that all crops and goods in the country get spoiled».

Fig. 139 - The violent storms («une tempeste si grant») which are raised by necromancers at the Lake of Pilate in the Sibillini Mountain Range, as mentioned in Antoine de la Sale's *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* (manuscript no. 0653 (0924), Bibliothèque du Château (Musée Condé), Chantilly, France, folium 4v)

This is nothing less than a clear reference to one of the central traits of the traditional legend concerning the cursed body of Pilate: the demons arousing frightful storms around his corpse.

In fact, we saw that both the river Tiber and the river Rhône were commoted and stirred by the presence of the dead prefect, with legions of rejoicing demons arousing tempests, lightnings, thunders and hail. Furthermore, storms and flames were issued from the pit in the Alps, too, in which the corpse had been cast, a collection of «deceptive illusions» («dyabolicae machinationes») created by the Fiend, as portrayed in the *Legenda Aurea*. So, we can confidently state that the legendary material reported to the French gentleman by the local people is basically the same we already encountered in the Pilate's legendary tale.

But it is the whole narrative reported by Antoine de la Sale which is fully immersed in the traditional literary lore concerning Pilatus. It is the French

writer himself who quotes a number of passages taken from Paulus Orosius, including the well-known excerpt which mentions the most famous report written by Pilate to his Emperor Tiberius in Rome, for centuries a main mythical item within the legend and lore concerning the Roman prefect:

«As Orosius reports in the second chapter of his eighth book, in which he says that after the death and resurrection of Jesus Christ Pilate sent to the said Tiberius the grand and amazing news about the trial, death and resurrection of a person called Jesus of Nazareth...».

[In the original French text: «Sicomme dit Orose ou second chappitre de son viii livre qui disioit que apres la mort et la resurrection de Jhesucrist pilate envoya au dit thibere cesar les treshaultes et merueilleuses nouvelles et le proces de la mort et resurrection du nomme Jhesus de Nazaret...»].

Fig. 140 - The Lakes of Pilate, a setting for the legendary tale of Pontius Pilate

Thus, with Antoine de la Sale's *Paradise of Queen Sibyl* we are facing one of the variants of a legendary tale which has journeyed through the millennia. A tale which concerns Pontius Pilate, his key role in the Passion of Jesus Christ, his unforgivable guilt and his final punishment, which continues after his own death. A variant of the tale which has been set, for

some reasons, in the icy lakes hidden within the peaks of the Sibillini Mountain Range, in Italy.

However, before we proceed further, there is one additional, discordant element we need to address.

In Antoine de la Sale's account, a chariot appears, drawn by two pairs of buffaloes. On the chariot, the dead body of Pilate lies, as it travels to his final destination of doom and curse.

Fig. 141 - A chariot transports the body of the dead roman prefect up to the lake set in the middle of the Sibillini Mountain Range: a grim vision of death from Antoine de la Sale's *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* (manuscript no. 0653 (0924), Bibliothèque du Château (Musée Condé), Chantilly, France, folium 4r)

A lugubrious, blood-curdling vision of death. A vision we have never encountered before in any of the ancient sources which are part of the legendary tale of Pontius Pilate.

What is this chariot? Why is it here? And why is it drawn by buffaloes? What has all that to do with Pilate and his gloomy legend?

For the first time ever, we will unveil the meaning of this odd, disturbing image. An image in which death plays a major part. As we will see in the next article.

23. The chariot, the buffaloes and the Triumph of Death

«Furthermore people said that when Pilate saw that there was no way left for him to save his own life, he asked to be granted a last wish, which was accorded to him: he demanded that after his death his body be placed on a chariot drawn by two pairs of buffaloes and allowed to wander wherever the buffaloes may lead it. And they tell this is what was actually done».

[In the original French text: «Encores disent les gens que quant pilate vit que de sa vie ny avoit nul remede plus, il supplia un don qui lui fut accorde alors requist que apres sa mort son corps feust mis sur un char attelle de deux paires de buffles et feust laissie aler la ou laventure des buffles le porteroit et ainsi dient que fut fait»].

This is the weird vision depicted by Antoine de la Sale in his *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl*, as he describes the tales on the Lakes of Pilate reported to him by the local peasants. A vision that the French writer intends to fully convey to his audience: the chariot, the buffaloes and the bleeding, loathsome corpse of the Roman prefect are portrayed in a miniature contained in manuscript no. 0653 (0924) preserved at Chantilly, France (folium 4r), as they slowly proceed in a sort of ghastly parade up the mountain-side to reach the looming waters of the lake.

«The buffaloes», continues de la Sale, «reached the shore of this lake and threw themselves into the waters together with all the chariot and Pilate's corpse [...]. And this is the reason for which this lake is called after Pilate» (in the original French text: «les bouffles vindrent au bourt de ce lac si se bouterent a tout le chair et le corps de pilate dedens [...]. Et pour ceste raison est dit le lac de pilate»).

Fig. 142 - Pontius Pilate, the chariot and the buffaloes from Antoine de la Sale's *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* (manuscript no. 0653 (0924), Bibliothèque du Château (Musée Condé), Chantilly, France, folium 4r)

Why does the legendary tale mention such a chariot? Why is it pulled by buffaloes? What is the meaning of such bizarre image?

We must note that all the ancient sources we perused with relation to the legendary tale of Pilate and his death do not provide any mention as to the journey of the corpse of the Roman prefect from Rome, to Vienne and the river Rhône in France, and finally to the Swiss Alps. If we open the pages of the *Legenda Aurea*, which includes all the listed steps of the ghastly travel, we only read that people moved the dead body from one resting place to the next one, and no detail on the transportation arrangements is provided (only generic verbs such as «deportaverunt», «commiserunt», «removerunt» are used, to signify that people simply took the corpse and brought it away to another place). And we find nothing in other texts as well, like *De Vita Pilati*.

No chariot nor buffaloes ever appear in previous sources which contain descriptions of the death of Pontius Pilate.

So why they are here?

Why the cursed corpse of a dead Pilate is brought from Rome to its resting place by this grim apparatus?

This does not happen by mere chance. As we will explain in this very article for the first time ever, this is a vision of the “Triumph of Death”.

Throughout the Middle Ages, the terror inspired by the inescapability of death, often in the horrible forms of plague, war and famine, was materialized in many pictorial representations of a victorious Death, crushing all living beings under its merciless curse. Death was portrayed in manuscripts, frescoes and tapestries in the act of taking the lives of all sorts of people, belonging to all social classes. Coming all of a sudden, Death was depicted by using several different narrative schemes, often morbid and grotesque, which were intended to arouse a dreadful awe in the beholders.

And, in many instances, especially in the late Middle Ages, triumphant Death arrived on a chariot led by couples of buffaloes.

A horrifying miniature is contained in manuscript Italien 545, preserved at the Bibliothèque Nationale de France, which contains the *Triumphs* by Petrarch, the illustrious Italian poet who lived in the fourteenth century. At folium 30v, we find a pictorial representation of the “Triumphus Mortis”: two black, fiendish buffaloes draw a triumphal carriage, on which Death holding a long lethal scythe stands. Beneath the hoofs of the animals, heaps of trampled bodies are crushed by the advancing, merciless wheels. The chariot is a sort of coffin, from which the spine-chilling laugh of the implacable skeleton runs across the countryside, while black demons bring away with them the souls of the dead.

Fig. 143 - The Triumph of Death, with the chariot and buffaloes, from Francesco Petrarca's *Triumphs*, in an impressive miniature contained in manuscript Italien 545 (Bibliothèque Nationale de France, Département des Manuscrits, folium 30v)

Another appalling image can be retrieved in manuscript no. 905 preserved at the Biblioteca Trivulziana in Milan. The fifteenth-century miniature which is found at folium 171v portrays, again from Petrarch's *Triumphs*, a triumphant Death, standing on its chariot, in the form of an antique sarcophagus, drawn by two buffaloes whose colour is as black as ultimate, eternal darkness.

Fig. 144 - Another representation of the Triumph of Death, with the chariot and buffaloes, from Francesco Petrarca's "Triumphs", a miniature contained in manuscript no. 905 (Biblioteca Trivulziana, Milan, folium 171v)

In manuscript Harley 2953 preserved at the British Library in London and dating to the first half of the sixteenth century, at folium 20 we find once more four skinny buffaloes, hellish and repulsive creatures, and the chariot of Death, crushing the mortals beneath its wheels, as it triumphantly proceeds and demons in the background snatch human souls away.

Fig. 145 - An instance of the Triumph of Death from a sixteenth-century Psalter contained in manuscript Harley 2953 (British Library, London, folium 20)

And another instance we find in a large tapestry dating to 1507, now at the Rijksmuseum in Amsterdam, and again inspired to Petrarch's *Triumphs*. In this complex allegorical scene, the four buffaloes draw a chariot on which a conquered Chastity lies, while the three Fates Atropos, Lachesis and Clotho, who represent Death, are in turn overwhelmed by Fame.

Many other instances of the chariot of Death can be found in other sources (e.g. Codex Palatinus 192 preserved at the Biblioteca Nazionale in Florence, folium 22r), often with reference to Petrarch and his work. It is most natural that animal-drawn hearses were used during the Middle Ages to convey dead persons to their burial places, and that oxen and domesticated buffaloes were preferred owing to their strength, slow though

unrelenting pace, and reliable behaviour, especially when raging plague claimed large number of lives.

Fig. 146 - The chariot and buffaloes from an early-sixteenth-century tapestry which depicts *The Triumph of Fame over Death* from Petrarch's *Triumphs* (Rijksmuseum, Amsterdam)

But what it is important to stress here is that, in this Italian variant of the legend of Pontius Pilate, the former prefect of Judaea, after his death in Rome, is taken in charge by Death itself. A triumphant Death, featuring its own peculiar signs: the chariot, a wheeled coffin which brings the dead to its final destination; and the buffaloes, the servants of the Grim Reaper, which inexorably proceed until they get to their final destination, a ghastly burial place.

A place where demons are waiting for the arrival of their prey. As it always appears in the ancient representations of the “Triumph of Death”. And as it always happens at Pontius Pilate's burial places, wherever they are set according to legend.

Here is the reason for the buffaloes and the chariot depicted by Antoine de la Sale. Pilate is escorted to his doom amid the Sibillini Mountain Range. And it is accompanied there with the most lugubrious, the most gruesome magnificence.

Why is this image present only in this Italian version of the legend? Why doesn't it show up in the standard, basically northern-European sources we have been perusing in the previous articles?

Possibly, Italy was imbued with the morbid taste for Death as presented by two major Italian authors who were active in the fourteenth century: Francesco Petrarca, whose *Triumphs* we already considered, and Giovanni Boccaccio, with his grisly description of the plague as contained in the *Decameron*. Possibly, in the Italian peninsula the chariot of Death was a known, almost popular image, as it was connected to the many artistic representations of Petrarca's *Triumphs* presented in several manuscripts and perhaps illustrated to frightened audiences in churches. Possibly, the oral tradition which developed in Italy found it appropriate and fascinating that an important personage like Pontius Pilate be accompanied to his doom by Death herself.

We must also remember that not many decades had passed since Black Death struck Europe and Italy in the years 1347-1352: the vision of ox-drawn carriages slowly passing by along the narrow streets of the medieval towns, loaded to their full capacity with heaps and heaps of corpses ravaged by the loathsome marks of the plague, still lingered in the eyes of the people (and in the eyes of Petrarch himself, who fully lived those appalling years and was hardly hit by multiple grievous losses), as an actual token of the Triumph of Death on earth. A vision that could not be included in the *Legenda Aurea*, written more than fifty years earlier, but able to assert all its grisly potential as an allegoric apparatus which was effectively integrated, some seventy years later, within the tale concerning the Lakes of Pilate in central Italy.

Thus, as a matter of fact, according to Antoine de la Sale's account, Pontius Pilate is brought to his fiendish burial place set within the glacial cirque of Mount Vettore by the chariot of Death.

And this must be considered as a wholly original feature of the Sibillini Mountain Range's version of the legend of Pilate.

24. Is this the end for a tale coming from elsewhere?

Now we are ready to confront with a most important question concerning the Sibillini Mountain Range, in Italy, and the Lakes of Pilate which are sitting beneath the dizzying crests of Mount Vettore, and in full view of Mount Sibyl, the focal point of another fascinating legend.

Fig. 147 - An impressive view of the glacial cirque of Mount Vettore with the Lakes of Pilate nested beneath precipitous crests

The question, of course, can be stated as follows: did the tradition concerning the burial place of Pontius Pilate actually emerge, as a fully original, native tale, from the Italian Sibillini Mountain Range? Was this lore generated in this Italian mountainous region, or was it transplated there from some different cultural areas and geographic territories into that specific, particular spot of land?

Was the Pilate's legend born there, or has it come from somewhere else?

The answer is fully known to researchers, and Arturo Graf, the Italian scholar who wrote his fundamental article *A Pilate Mount in Italy* in the year 1893, had already it clear in his mind.

Fig. 148 - The article on the Italian Lakes of Pilate from Arturo Graf's *Myths, legends and superstitions of the Middle Ages* (1893), pag. 143

Because the answer is quite straightforward: the Italian Lakes of Pilate are nothing else but the product of the transferral of Pontius Pilate's literary and oral tradition, which can be traced in a number of apocryphal texts whose original setting was in France and Switzerland, to a remote region of the Italian Apennines, where mysterious lakes stood, and still stand.

The cursed corpse of the prefect of Judaea has never been cast into the icy waters of the sinister lakes hidden within the glacial cirque of Mount Vettore. Or, better, the relevant tradition has nothing to do with those specific lakes.

We may remind the reader that, in a previous paper (*Birth of a Sibyl: the medieval connection*), we posed a same sort of question with relation to the Apennine Sibyl and her magical kingdom hidden beneath the Sibyl's peak. And the answer was quite the same: the lore concerning a Sibyl living in a mountain was born elsewhere, in far-away countries, as it showed significant connections with the Matter of Britain and the ancient literary characters of Morgan le Fay and her friend Sebile.

However, the search for an answer as to the case of the Apennine Sibyl was a harder task. With the Sibyl, the investigation required the identification, unfolding and final removal of a number of extraneous, additional narrative layers which concealed the true origin of the Italian legend about that Sibyl. Careful research was needed to find out the elements borrowed from several different mythical tales, so as to get to the true essence of the local legend.

In the present case, the task was much easier.

Since the very beginning, it was clear that Pontius Pilate featured a number of different legendary resting places, actually too many: a circumstance that manifestly hinted to a process of contamination which promoted a process of diffusion of the same legendary tale across different regions and territories. After having scrutinised the main available textual sources, and having determined that no one of them ever mentioned the Sibillini Mountain Range, it became apparent that the Lakes of Pilate in Italy had just inherited a legend that was rooted elsewhere in Europe, namely Vienne and the river Rhône in France, with a specific link to the place of exile of Herod Archelaus as quoted by first-century historian Flavius Josephus, and then Rome and its river Tiber, Saint-Chamond and its Massif de Pilat in the region of Vienne, and then Lausanne and Lucerne in Switzerland, with the Tomlishorn, or Mont Pilate.

Therefore, the Lakes of Pilate in Italy have nothing to do with the legend of Pontius Pilate, the way it has been developing itself across the oral and literary tradition throughout more than a thousand years.

What Antoine de la Sale found on May 18th, 1420 during his visit to the Sibillini Mountain Range, was no original legend: it was rather a transplant of a foreign legendary tale into the sinister setting of that specific portion of

the Italian Apennines which rises between the provinces of Umbria and Marche.

Pontius Pilate lived and died elsewhere. He never came to Mount Vettore on a chariot drawn by black, demonic buffaloes. Neither in actual truth nor in the original core of the legend.

However, is this the end of our story?

Are we going a road that is about to lead us to a melancholic ending, with a desolate abasement of the Lakes of Pilate, from a thrilling mystery to a mere variant of a legend that belongs to other lands?

Are those lakes now exposed as bare water basins, deprived of all their eerie fascination?

Fig. 149 - The still, sinister waters of the Lakes of Pilate

Is that the end of the legend of the Lakes of Pilate?

The answer to all these questions is the same as already provided with relation to the Apennine Sibyl in our previous paper *Birth of a Sibyl: the medieval connection*.

The answer is no. This is not the end. The enigma is still there, and it thrives with all its dark, sinister glow over the remote peaks of the Sibillini Mountain Range. At the very center of Italy.

As we will see in the final section of this paper.

25. When an Italian lake became the 'Lake of Pilate'

In the preceding chapters, we saw that the Lakes of Pilate, the two icy, crystal-like surfaces set within the sinister glacial cirque of Mount Vettore, in the Sibillini Mountain Range, have harboured for centuries a gloomy legend connected to the figure of Pontius Pilate, the Roman prefect of Judaea at the time of the Passion. However, the tale which was narrated about the lakes, as reported by Antoine de la Sale in his *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl*, was just a transplant of a medieval legend with an illustrious literary ancestry: a myth on Pilate's burial place that had its setting in different areas of Europe, far from the Italian central Apennines, which nothing had to do with those eerie, fascinating lakes.

Fig. 150 - The Lake of Pilate as it appears in Antoine de la Sale's *La Salade* (version printed in Paris, 1527)

Thus, the legend about Pilate was not originated in the Sibillini Mountain Range: at some time, during the centuries of the Middle Ages, it was adapted, through an elaboration carried out in Italy by oral tradition, to a specific lake sitting in the middle of the Italian Apennines.

But when did this re-working and adaptation process occur?

There are many clues which we may try to follow. Let's go into each one of them in detail.

The first clue is provided to us by thirteenth-century *Legenda Aurea*. This huge, most successful work contains the most recent and most comprehensive description of the legend that concerns Pontius Pilate, with the indication of the many legendary burial places for the prefect's cursed corpse: the Tiber, Vienne and the Rhône, Lausanne and the Alps. From the time of its publication onwards, often in gorgeous editions, everybody in Europe became fully acquainted with the odd, frightful tale concerning the doom of the Roman prefect of Judaea. And the earliest manuscripts of the *Legenda Aurea* date back to the end of the thirteenth century, just before Jacobus de Varagine's death, which occurred in 1298.

Fig. 151 - The chapter on St. Michael the Archangel from a most beautiful manuscript of the *Legenda Aurea* dating to the late fifteenth century (Rps BOZ 11, Biblioteka Narodowa, Poland, pag. 218)

The *Legenda* does not mention the Italian lake in the Sibillini Mountain Range as a burial place for Pilate. So, re-working of the legend, with its adaptation to the Apennines, should have taken place not earlier than the final decade of the thirteenth century, so as to skip any chance of inclusion in the latest versions of Jacobus' work.

Fig. 152 - The *Triumph of Death*, a detail from a painted piece of wooden furniture by fifteenth-century Tuscan painter Francesco di Stefano, also known as Pesellino (Isabella Stewart Gardner Museum, Boston)

A second clue is given by our well-known chariot with its pulling buffaloes. This is but a suggestive hypothesis; however, we cannot refrain from thinking that the Italian re-elaboration of the legend was indelibly and harrowingly imprinted by the ghastly recollection of the horrifying chariots full of dead bodies which were to be seen in the narrow streets of many Italian towns during the lethal, implacable plague that ravaged the

peninsula from 1347 onwards. This is a peculiar detail which is not present at all in the earlier *Legenda Aurea*, nor in any other relevant medieval text linked to the legend of Pilate, so we might envisage that the Italian version of the legend of Pontius Pilate was re-worked after the middle decades of the fourteenth century.

A third clue comes to us from a work written by a fourteenth-century poet from Tuscany: Fazio degli Uberti.

Fig. 153 - The opening folium of Fazio degli Uberti's *Dittamondo* in a manuscript dating to 1447 (Bibliothèque Nationale de France, Département des Manuscrits, Italien 81)

Fazio's *Dittamondo*, written in the second half of the fourteenth century and never completed (the poet died in 1367), contains the earliest mention ever retrieved about the Lake of Pilate, set in what we know today as the Sibillini Mountain Range. And here is what our Tuscan poet says, as taken

from manuscript Italien 81, preserved at the Bibliothèque Nationale de France:

«I don't want to overlook the renown of the Mount of Pilate, where a lake is - which in summers is carefully guarded by watches on duty - because here Simon the Sorcerer ascends to consecrate his spellbook - so that troublesome tempests are aroused- according to what local people say».

[In the original Italian text: «la fama qui non vo' rimagna nuda - del monte di pillato, dov'è il lago - che si guarda l'estate a muda a muda - però che qua s'intende in Simon mago - per sagrar il suo libro in su monta - onde tempesta poi con grande smago - secondo che per quei di là si conta»].

Fig. 154 - Fazio degli Uberti's verses on the Lake of Pilatus drawn from his *Dittamondo* (Bibliothèque Nationale de France, Département des Manuscrits, Italien 81, folium 95v)

This is the first time in history that a reference to a lake named after Pontius Pilate, set between the town of Norcia and the Italian province of the Marche, is found in written literature.

The listed verses were written somewhere between 1350 and 1367. Again, we find ourselves in a time period not earlier than the second half of the fourteenth century.

Before 1350, we have nothing.

Or, better, we have something. Something that was written around 1335. But, in it, there isn't the slightest reference to Pontius Pilate.

Pontius Pilate is not mentioned at all. But that lake, it is mentioned indeed.

And this mention is the eeriest quote we might ever stumble upon.

26. A dark presence was there before Pilate came

«I heard a remarkable, horrific tale about Norcia, the Italian town, that was reported to me as an absolutely proven truth by a certain prelate, a trustworthy person indeed among all men» (in the original Latin text: «Exemplum terribile esse circa Norciam Italie civitatem audivi pro vero et pro centies experto narrari a quodam praelato summe inter alios fide digno»).

Fig. 155 - The excerpt on the Lake of Norcia taken from Petrus Berchorius' *Reductorium Morale* (Bibliothèque Nationale de France, Département des Manuscrits, Latin 16786, folium 301v)

This is the opening remark of a stunning excerpt found in a precious fourteenth-century manuscript: the *Reductorium Morale* by Petrus Berchorius (Pierre Bersuire), a French benedictine monk and abbot, who lived between 1290 and 1362 and was a member of the papal court in Avignon, known for his erudition and his learned literary works.

In our previous article *The Lake of Pilatus in an antique manuscript: Pierre Bersuire and the fourteenth century dark renown of Norcia's lake*, we already published this astounding excerpt (Book XIV, Chapter 30 “About Italy”) taken from one of the ancient manuscripts of the *Reductorium Morale*. Manuscript Latin 16786, preserved at the Bibliothèque Nationale

de France, contains this most remarkable quote on the Lake of Norcia (also known today as the 'Lakes of Pilatus'): the parchment folia date to 1399, however Berchorius' text is much older, as it was probably written in 1335.

And, in this most ancient text, which precedes Antoine de la Sale's *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* of more than a century, we find Norcia and its lake; however, we find no reference at all to Pontius Pilate:

«Amid the peaks which raise near that town [Norcia] there is a lake, which from antique times is sacred to demons and conspicuously inhabited by them; today, no men but necromancers can get to the lake without being killed by the demons. Because of that, walls were built around the shore of the lake, and watched over by guards, lest necromancers be allowed to access the place to consecrate their books to the demons».

[In the original Latin text: «Inter montes isti civitati proximos esse lacum ab antiquis daemonibus consecratum et ab ipsis sensibiliter inhabitatum, ad quem nullus hodie praeter necromanticos potest accedere, quin a daemonibus occidat. Igitur circa terminos lacus facti sunt muri qui a custodibus servantur, ne necromantici pro liberis suis consecrandis daemonibus illuc accedere permittantur»].

Fig. 156 - The subsequent passage on the Lake of Norcia as taken from Petrus Berchorius' *Reductorium Morale* (Bibliothèque Nationale de France, Département des Manuscrits, Latin 16786, folium 301v)

As we can see, the earliest text we have about the Lakes of Pilate, written as early as the first half of the fourteenth century, does not convey the slightest reference to the name of Pontius Pilate and the legend connected to the burial of the body of the Roman prefect of Judaea into the Italian lake, as in later literary works, such as Antoine de la Sale's. Instead, it provides a most important confirmation: the lake was a place used to practice necromancy, because demons lived in there. And that was known since antiquity.

But Berchorius never writes the word 'Pilatus'. He goes straight to the inner nucleus of the lake's myth. And this nucleus is definitely dark:

«And about that lake the most horrifying thing is what follows: each year that town [Norcia] sends a single man, a living man, beyond the walls that encircle the lake, as an offering to the demons, who immediately and in full view tear apart and slaughter that man; and people say that if the town does not comply, the country would be razed by the storms. Every year the town selects a certain criminal, and sends him there to the demons as a tribute».

Fig. 157 - Ghastly offerings at the Lake of Norcia as reported by Petrus Berchorius in his *Reductorium Morale* (Bibliothèque Nationale de France, Département des Manuscrits, Latin 16786, folium 301v)

[In the original Latin text: «Est ergo istud ibi summe terribile, quia civitas illa omni anno unum hominem vivum pro tributo infra ambitum murorum iuxta lacum ad daemones mittunt, qui statim visibiliter illum hominem

lacerant et consumunt, quod (ut aiunt) si civitas non facit, patria tempestatibus deperiret. Civitas ergo annuatim aliquem sceleratum eligit que pro tributo daemonibus illuc mittit»].

What is the meaning of all that?

The meaning is thoroughly stunning.

We have a lake with demons in it, and devastating storms. Just like in the legendary tradition connected to the burial places (Vienne, the Rhône, Saint-Chamond, Lausanne) of the cursed body of Pontius Pilate.

But here, in the middle of the remote, sinister Sibillini Mountain Range, there is no Pilate. In the early fourteenth century, there was no need to add any Pontius Pilate to mark the lake of Norcia with an eerie touch.

Fig. 158 - The sinister spell of the Lakes of Pilate

What Petrus Berchorius is telling us with in *Reductorium Morale* is that the lake sitting in the glacial cirque of Mount Vettore was already cursed by

itself. It did have its own demons and tempests, with no necessity for further mythical explanations, like a plunge by a Roman prefect's dead body.

The legend of the lake of Norcia was already alive at that time, with no connection to Pontius Pilate and his elaborated medieval lore.

In ancient times, a sinister fascination already issued from what we know today as the Lakes of Pilate. And it had nothing to do with the Roman prefect of Judaea.

27. A recap and a final question

We are about to conclude our astounding journey across the legend of Pontius Pilate, and the legend of the Lakes of Pilate set in the middle of the Sibillini Mountain Range, in central Italy.

We had a close encounter with a historical figure: Pontius Pilate, the fifth prefect of Judaea from 26 A.D. to 36 A.D., an official of the Roman Empire who played a key role in the Passion of Jesus Christ. We read the words that were written on him by classical authors such as Flavius Josephus and Philo of Alexandria, and, of course, the passages which mention Pilate in the canonical Gospels.

Fig. 159 - Pontius Pilate

We perused the words of the Fathers of the Church who, since the earliest centuries of Christianity, addressed a tricky issue: did Pilate actually make substantial efforts to set Jesus free from the accusations that were made against him by the Jews? Or, did he eventually leave the Son of God to his doom of death on the Cross? Across the centuries, different answers were pronounced which led to consider the Roman prefect either as a saint or a servant to the Evil.

Then we ventured ourselves into the Middle Ages, and found that many apocryphal works on Pontius Pilate were circulating throughout Europe, certainly arising from a mesh of oral tales which were narrated before fascinated audiences belonging to all social classes. We saw that the prefect of Judaea has treaded the medieval centuries attracting ever-growing legendary accounts on his life, deeds, final prosecution by an almost Christianised Emperor, be it Tiberius or Vespasian, and final death.

And we saw that the tales on Pilate provided many details on his ultimate resting place as well.

Actually, there was more than one single resting place. And all such places were infested by demons.

Be it the Tiber in Rome, or the river Rhône by the French town of Vienne, or a marsh or a pit in the Swiss Alps, the fiendish corpse of Pontius Pilate was not to find any rest: demons awaited his arrival and rejoiced in his company, arousing storms and tempests at the very spot of the prefect's burial.

This is similar, so similar to what Antoine de la Sale narrated in his *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl*, dating to the first half of the fifteenth century: in the vicinity of Mount Sibyl, a Lake of Pilate housed exactly the same story, with the addition of a chariot and buffaloes, a canonical image of the Triumph of Death. And his story portrays the same tempests.

However, not a single manuscripted work belonging to the medieval tradition on the cursed burial place of Pilate, including *De Vita Pilati* and the *Legenda Aurea*, ever mentions the Apennines or the region around Mount Sibyl as one of Pontius Pilate's haunted resting places.

The legendary narration is certainly the same, but the Lakes of Pilate and the Sibillini Mountain Range do not seem to be part of it. Especially when we consider that the earliest retrievable mention about our Italian lake, as found in Petrus Berchorius' *Reductorium Morale*, does report about the presence of demons, but at the same time does not provide any mention of the name of Pilate.

Therefore, we concluded, sure enough the legend was not born here: as a matter of fact, it was transplanted to this place, deeply set within the glacial cirque of Mount Vettore, as an extraneous mythical material. And the myth was possibly transferred to this location around the beginning of the second half of the fourteenth century.

The final question is: why?

28. The mountains still hide their ultimate enigma

At some moment in time, possibly during the fourteenth century, a sinister tale concerning the cursed burial place of Pontius Pilate settled right in the middle of what we know today as the Sibillini Mountain Range, in the Italian Apennines.

Why did so odd an occurrence happen?

Sure enough, it did not happen by mere chance.

Maybe our readers remember what we wrote in another research paper, with reference to another legend which lives in the very same territory. In *Birth of a Sibyl - The medieval connection*, we asked ourselves the following question: why such tales and stories did elect to stop exactly there, amid the peaks of the Sibillini Mountain Range?

The above question was posed with reference to the legend of the Apennine Sibyl and its lineage from written and oral narratives concerning Morgan le Fay and the enchantress Sebile, both pertaining to the illustrious tradition of the Matter of Britain.

Fig. 160 - Mount Sibyl in the Sibillini Mountain Range, the legendary abode of the Apennine Sibyl

But the very same consideration can be re-stated, in the present paper, with reference to the legendary tale concerning the Lakes of Pilate.

We wrote that the Sibyl's legend was transplanted into the Sibillini Mountain Range from some different cultural areas and geographic territories: a transferral into that specific, particular spot of land. This is also true for Pontius Pilate.

We wrote that the Apennine Sibyl is the final outcome of an evolutionary process which settled eventually down in the area that is known today under the name of Sibillini Mountain Range. This is also true for the legend which refers to Pilate's burial place.

We asked ourselves whether we were treading a path that was about to lead to a sad final destination merely consisting in a sorrowful 'downgrade' of

the Apennine Sibyl, from an independent, original myth to a sheer adaptation of legends developed elsewhere.

And the answer was no.

We wrote that, as a matter of fact, that was not the end of the Apennine Sibyl's legend. Likewise, this is not the end of the legend of the Lakes of Pilate. In the very same way.

Because Pontius Pilate, a fascinating historical and mythical figure as he is, is not enough to explain why it all happened.

The enigma which concerns the Lakes of Pilate is everything but solved.

Because now the question is: for what reason did the lore about Pontius Pilate establish itself by these lakes? Why such a gloomy tale did elect to stop exactly there, amid the peaks of the Sibillini Mountain Range? Why this extraordinary narrative settled down precisely in this spot, lost amid the mountainous fastnesses of the Italian Apennines?

Fig. 161 - The Lakes of Pilate in the Sibillini Mountain Range, which house the legend of Pontius Pilate's cursed body

As we already wrote with reference to the Apennine Sibyl, the legendary narrative material belonging to the ancient lore concerning the burial places traditionally assigned to Pontius Pilate (Rome and the Tiber, Vienne and the Rhône, Saint-Chamond, Lausanne and the Alps), might as well have landed at any other location in Italy or elsewhere, depositing its mythical charge into a different place, so as to set up a brand new branch of the legend concerning a demonic resting place at any other lake or marsh or mountain across the Italian Apennines, from Liguria to Calabria. Anywhere else.

But the legend established itself right here: in the middle of the Sibillini Mountain Range.

What sort of magnetic pull did attract the magical tale about Pontius Pilate to the glacial cirque of Mount Vettore? For what kind of fated chance did the prefect's sinister narrative come to rest, like a ball spinning on a roulette wheel, right into the position marked by this remote Italian mountain?

The land of Italy is scattered of hundreds of lakes, peaks and mountaintops: why weren't they fit to house a legend on demons and dead bodies?

Why the Lakes of Pilate?

No scholar has ever addressed this issue. We found no answers on that in Arturo Graf, who is the only author who explicitly addressed the matter. No research paper has ever dealt with this fundamental question.

And wholly nonsensical appears to be the popular argument which ascribes the dark, fiendish fame of the lake to the presence of the poor, small, utterly frail *Chirocephalus Marchesonii*, the tiny coral-red shrimp which merrily swims and drifts across the icy waters of the Lakes of Pilate: no awe-inspiring demon can be shaped in any medieval mind by this gentle, inoffensive little animal, not to mention any mythical capacity that might be ascribed to it as to raising violent storms, if not perfectly minuscule.

Of course, there is more to it.

Because the fundamental issue of our whole search, the most critical one, is the following: it actually appears that both the Lakes of Pilate and the

Apennine Sibyl arose from some odd condensation of a peculiar nature which marks this place, the Sibillini Mountain Range.

Fig. 162 - A close view of the *Chirocephalus Marchesonii*, the small inoffensive shrimp which inhabits the waters of the Lakes of Pilate

There is a sort of original core pertaining to both legends: something that was not transplanted from any other place or tradition, something that was born right here instead, and possibly connected to the fact that this location is some genre of very special site.

We have to keep in mind one major aspect. It is certainly true that Antoine de la Sale, at folium 2v of his *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* reports that the mountain which houses the lake is a place «which some name the mountain of the lake of Pilate» (in the original French text: «que aucuns appellent le mont du lac de pillate»). But, just in the very same line, he adds that the lake's name is much more remarkable:

«Mountain of the lake of Queen Sibyl» (in the original French text: «Mont du lac de la royne sibille»).

Fig. 163 - The Lake of Pilate also known as the Lake of Queen Sibyl as reported in Antoine de la Sale's *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* (manuscript no. 0653 (0924), Bibliothèque du Château (Musée Condé), Chantilly, France, folium 2v)

And this very remark is stated again in the drawing of the mount and lake proposed by Antoine de la Sale at folium 5v.

Fig. 164 - The Lake of Pilate / Lake of Queen Sibyl from the drawing contained in Antoine de la Sale's *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* (manuscript no. 0653 (0924), Bibliothèque du Château (Musée Condé), Chantilly, France, folium 5v)

And he also re-states it at folia 4r-4v: «Others call it the lake of the Sibyl because Mount Sibyl is right before it and connected to the lake, apart from a small streamlet which runs between them in the way portrayed in the following figure» («Les autres l'appellent le lac de la sibille pour ce que le mont de la sibille est devant et joignant a cestu fors dun petit ruisseau qui court entre deux en la maniere que cy apres est pourtrait»).

Fig. 165 - The Lake of both Pilate and the Sibyl from Antoine de la Sale's *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* (manuscript no. 0653 (0924), Bibliothèque du Château (Musée Condé), Chantilly, France, folia 4r and 4v)

The Lakes of Pilate are not Pilate's. They are the Lakes of the Sibyl.

And there is another point not to be forgotten. A point which makes the Lakes and Cave further closer one another.

In our previously-released research paper *Apennine Sibyl: the bright side and the dark side*, we mentioned a passage about the Sibyl's cave taken from *De la hayne de Satan et malins esprist contro l'homme*, a treatise written in the sixteenth century by Pierre Crespet, also known as 'Crespetus', a Celestinian monk. In his work, in which he extensively elaborates on the Sibyl of Norcia, we find the following words:

«When a necromancer or other person talks to the Sibyl, storms and lightnings are stirred frightfully across the whole land».

[In the original French text: «quand on communique avec elle, soyt magicien ou autre, les tempestes & foudres s'esmouvent horriblement par tout le pais»].

Because we saw, in that paper, that the Apennine Sibyl was considered as an evil being ranked in the fiendish class of 'subterranean demon', for which the German Benedictine abbot Johannes Trithemius, in his *Liber octo quaestionum ad Maximilianum Cesarem* published in 1515, wrote that «they can cause wind and flames to erupt from holes in the ground» («hiatus efficiunt terrae ventosque flaminomos suscitant»).

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d'effet comme i'ay dit ailleurs, ledit Mirabile deposa deuant les luges qu'un autre sien compaignon nommé l'Escot qui a l'og temps rodé en France fameux Necromatié, & a ioué des tours de son mestier deuant les Princes & Seigneurs qui ont esté à son escolle & n'y ont rié appris de bon, qu'il auoit esté cōsulté la Sibylle fameuse que les voyageurs d'Italie assurent estre en vne grotte ou carrière proche de la ville de Nufse en Italie laquelle il dit estre de basse stature assise en vne petite chaise les cheueux perdans jusques à terre, laquelle luy donna vn liure cōsacré, & luy meit dans vn agneau qu'il auoit au doigt vn esprit, par le moy desquels liure & esprit il eust la puissance d'aller en tous lieux où il souhaitoit estre transporté moyennat que le vent ne fust contraire. Dit dauantage que le Pape fait soigneusement garder laditte carrière où est laditte Sibylle, pour empescher la cōmunicatiō avec elle, & n'y a que ceux qui sōt magiciés, & y peuuēt inuisiblement entrer qui la puisēt aborder, à cause que quād on cōmunique avec elle, soyt magicié ou autre, les tēpestes & foudres s'esmouuēt horriblemēt par tout le païs, & afin qu'ō ne pēse cecy estre fa-

Sibylle desur se cōsultee par l'Escot in signe magicien.

le vent ne fust contraire. Dit dauantage que le Pape fait soigneusement garder laditte carrière où est laditte Sibylle, pour empescher la cōmunicatiō avec elle, & n'y a que ceux qui sōt magiciés, & y peuuēt inuisiblement entrer qui la puisēt aborder, à cause que quād on cōmunique avec elle, soyt magicié ou autre, les tēpestes & foudres s'esmouuēt horriblemēt par tout le païs, & afin qu'ō ne pēse cecy estre fa-

*Hos ventos vel Dijs acrij vel fideya mittunt,
Sepa etenim cum thesauris tellure latentis,
Vult auferre Magus vel consecrare libellum,
Vel magico ritu quemquam sibi subdere diuum.*

Fig. 166 - Tempests arising from the Sibyl's cave as reported by Pierre Crespet (Crespetus) in his *De la hayne de Satan et malins esprist contro l'homme* (Paris 1590), pag. 93

citatis imperat; neq; scis angelis familiares esse meretur. si qui vero in illi sanctitatis gradum p̄fecerint quo miracula facientes in ecclesia quādamodū sc̄i quōdā p̄fecerunt; iam potenter & impare demonib; possunt et familiare beatorū spiritū habere cōfortiū. Certū est enī q; sc̄i & deo dilecti hoies in primitiua xp̄ianorū ecclesia maiora quōdā bonorū cooperatione spiritū b̄ficiā p̄ferere mortalibus; q; prauorū hominū impietas maleficia demonū ministeriū vnq; inferre potuisset. Multa enim potest miranda precantibus; quisquis dei cultor verus similis euaserit angelis sc̄tis.

DE POTESTATE

Maleficarum. Questio Sexta.

Sexta inuictissime maiestatis tue questio fuit, Vnde potestas hec ita maleficis, qua patrat tam multa varia & mirabilia in vna hora; quia vel quare crete possit in oi vita sua. Ad huc uiter uoluerimus n̄derere; necessitas a dño deo est; sine quo nihil potest fieri. Dicit enī in sc̄o euāgelio christus testis facere Vnde manifestū est q; dicit aliquid hominib; a dño deo & si siue bonū hoies siue malū operentur. In huiusmodi p̄sul Augustin; dicit. Volūtas dei est prima & summa causa om̄iū corporaliū specierū ac motionū; nihilq; p̄c̄i ista totū creature amplissima & immēta republica visibilis; qd nō de iteriori iusibili atq; itelligibili aula summi impatoris aut iubeat; aut p̄mittatur / secundū ineffabile iusticiā premiorū atq; penarū. Vnde non est dubitandū Cesar q; potestas illa maleficarū / in q; mirandos (cooperatione demonū) horrendosq; p̄ducunt effectū a dño deo

in ciuitatib; in terra latentis querunt; in pernicie humani generis paratissimi. Hiatus efficiunt terre / ventosq; flammiosos inscitant; & fundamenta edificiorū cōcutiūt. Noctibus aliqñ de montibus turmatim egressi mirant;

Fig. 167 - Subterranean demons and fiendish storms from Johannes Trithemius' *Liber octo quaestionum ad Maximilianum Cesarem* (Oppenheim, 1515), in the *Quaestio Sexta - De potestate maleficarum*

The Lakes and the Cave. The same demons. The same tempests. The same destruction.

We are getting to a far-reaching conclusion, a new and exciting starting point.

Mount Vettore and Mount Sibyl. The Lakes of Pilate and the Sibyl's Cave. The two legends are linked together in some mysterious way. An enigmatic connection that is still to be unveiled.

But how could we ever think that the two legends are unrelated, if we consider that the two sites are only five miles apart from each other, and in full mutual view?

Fig. 168 - A vision of the Sibillini Mountain Range showing the positions of the Lakes of Pilate and the Sibyl's Cave

Our thrilling enquiry is not over. We have unfolded the heavy chivalric layers which sheltered from view the inner, most genuine core of the Apennine Sibyl's legend. We have found Morgan le Fay and Sebile. And we have also walked in company of Pontius Pilate, a legendary tale that has its roots elsewhere in Europe, and has settled here, by the gloomy waters

that were already inhabited by demons, and were considered as Lakes of the Sibyl.

But, still, we have not reached the true nucleus of both myths.

There is something more to it. Something sinister, something obscure which has magnetized all that mythical might, both literary and oral, onto that specific place of Earth: an Italian mountainous range, lost in the middle of the Apennines.

We need to go further. We need to fully unfold the residual additions that still conceal the main, focal point of the legends of Mount Sibyl and the Lakes of Pilate. The point from which it all began.

Our work is not finished yet. The mystery is not still solved. The enigma still lies there.

Because the legends of the Apennine Sibyl and the Lakes of Pilate are not dead at all. We want to clutch their ultimate secret in our hands. We want to find out who they really are.

The hunt for the secret of the Sibillini Mountain Range is not over.

And we are now ready, as we will see in a further series of article we will soon publish, for the final, decisive step.

A step that will unveil the very nature, and the true semblance, of these fascinating legends.

Michele Sanvico

END OF PART 3

**Please refer to Part 1 and Part 2
for the previous sections of this research paper**